

Determination of Work Productivity of Members of the Biak Sector III Command: The Role of Work Attitude, Skills, and Efficiency

Slamet Suhartono¹, Mokhammad Natsir², Umu Khouruh³

^{1,2,3} University of Merdeka Malang

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 06 February 2026	Work productivity is a strategic factor in improving organizational performance, especially in defense institutions that demand high effectiveness and efficiency in task performance. This study aims to analyze the influence of work attitudes, skill levels, and efficiency on the work productivity of members of the Biak Sector III Command, both simultaneously and partially, and to identify the variables with the most significant influence. This study uses a quantitative, explanatory research design. The study population comprises all Tamtama and Bintara members in the Operational Service of the Biak Sector III Command, totaling 68 people; therefore, the sampling technique used is a census. Data were collected through questionnaires that had been tested for validity and reliability, and then analyzed using multiple linear regression in SPSS. The results of the study indicate that work attitudes, skill levels, and efficiency simultaneously have a significant effect on the work productivity of members of the Biak Sector III Command. All three independent variables positively influence work productivity, with efficiency exerting the most significant effect. These findings indicate that increasing member productivity can be achieved by strengthening positive work attitudes, continuous skill development, and optimizing resource use. This research provides an empirical contribution to the development of human resource management, particularly in the context of defense organizations. It can serve as a basis for formulating strategic policies to increase members' productivity.
Corresponding Author: Slamet Suhartono	
KEYWORDS: work attitude, skill level, efficiency, work productivity, human resource management.	

1. INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization, the quality of human resources is a significant concern in determining organizational success. Organizations can develop (advance) due to the ability of their employees to produce high performance. The higher an employee's performance, the greater the organization's success (Wati & Rahman, 2020). In this context, work productivity reflects the concrete behavior demonstrated by each individual, as evidenced by the work results achieved by employees in accordance with their roles within an agency. This also includes the level of effectiveness and efficiency demonstrated by employees in carrying out daily tasks within an organization or company over a given period (Sari et al., 2020; Husain et al., 2022).

According to the Encyclopedia Britannica (in Sedarmayanti, 2019), productivity in economics means the ratio of the results achieved to the sacrifices made to produce something. The general definition of work productivity is the comparison between the results achieved (output) and the

total human resources used (input). According to Sedarmayanti (2019: 72), several factors can influence employee work productivity, namely: a)—work Attitude, b) Skill Level, and c) Efficiency.

Employee skills can also include areas that need improvement. Skills are an individual's ability to perform a specific, focused, yet dynamic task, requiring time to learn and being demonstrable (Rustiana et al., 2021).

Based on the background of the problem and the formulation of the problem, the objectives of this study are to describe the work attitude, skill level, efficiency and work productivity of Members of the Biak Sector III Command; analyze the level of significance of Work Attitude, Skill Level, and Efficiency simultaneously having a significant effect on the work productivity of Members of the Biak Sector III Command; analyze the level of significance of Work Attitude, Skill Level, and Efficiency partially having a significant effect on the work productivity of Members of the Biak Sector III Command; analyze which variables of Work

“Determination of Work Productivity of Members of the Biak Sector III Command: The Role of Work Attitude, Skills, and Efficiency”

Attitude, Skill Level, and Efficiency have a dominant effect on the work productivity of Members of the Biak Sector III Command.

The expected results of this research for Kmando Sector III Biak are practical, namely it can be used as input for practitioners and the Biak Sector III Command, so that they can find out how the Members' attitudes towards the variables of Work Attitude, Skill Level, and Efficiency towards the work productivity of members and can also be used as a reference in taking strategic steps in order to increase the work productivity of members of the Biak Sector III Command.

The expected results of this research for the author are to increase insight in the field of human resource management, especially regarding the influence of Work Attitude, Skill Level, and efficiency on the work productivity of Members of the Biak Sector III Command; as a form of direct application of theories regarding Work Attitude, Skill Level, and Efficiency, and the work productivity of Members of the Biak Sector III Command, which were obtained during lectures into real field situations.

The expected results of this research for the development of science are theoretically related to the development of science, especially those related to Work Attitude, Skill Level, and Efficiency and productivity of the members of the Biak Sector III Command. There are developments in science, especially in human resource management, which have recently been of great interest to various groups. Thus, the results of this research are expected to be used as one of the reference materials for the demands of the development of increasingly complex human resource management, as well as a reference for further research, especially those related to the topic of Work Attitude, Skill Level, Efficiency, and productivity of the members of the Biak Sector III Command.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Sukardi (2021) states that work productivity is an individual's success in carrying out their duties and can be measured along the dimensions of engagement, planning skills, effort, and overall employee productivity. Setiawan (2021) states that work productivity is the ratio of output (results) to input (inputs). If productivity increases, it can only be achieved by improving efficiency (time, materials, labor) and work systems, as well as production techniques and workforce skills. Kustini and Sari (2020) state that work productivity is the ability to produce goods or services using the resources and abilities of each worker or employee.

Feist in Fauzan (2018: 45) Attitude is a pattern of traits and characteristics that are relatively permanent and provide both consistency and individuality to the behavior a person will carry out and highlight. At the same time, Robbins in Fauzan (2018: 45) Work Attitude is in the form of three

components (aspects), namely the evaluation aspect (cognitive component) and strong feelings (affective component), which will guide a behavior (component of the tendency to do good or bad things).

A person's expertise is reflected in how well they perform specific activities, such as operating equipment, communicating, and so on. Therefore, skill is the ability to carry out a particular task, both physically and mentally (Budi W. Soetjipto, 2022). Furthermore, according to Fauzi (2020: 7), skill can refer to the specific actions performed or the nature in which the skill is implemented. Many activities are considered skills, consisting of several skills, and a person's degree of mastery reflects their level of skill. This occurs because it is generally accepted that one or more extended movement patterns or behaviors can be called skills, for example, writing, playing the guitar or piano, adjusting a machine, walking, running, jumping, and so on. When this is used, the word "skill" is meant as a noun.

According to Stoner (2018), efficiency is the ability to minimize resource use to achieve organizational goals. A person who acts efficiently can minimize the cost of the resources required. Work efficiency is the implementation of activities in the easiest, cheapest, shortest, lightest, and shortest-in-distance ways to reach the goal. Efficiency is a measure of the success of an activity, as reflected in the resources used to achieve the desired results.

3. METHOD

3.1 Research Design

The research design is quantitative, meaning it involves a hypothesis and uses statistical tools to test it. This research is a causal-comparative study with three independent variables and one dependent variable. The results of the influence between the variables studied will be explained in more depth, making this research explanatory.

3.2 Scope of Research

The scope of this research includes human resources research, specifically examining the work productivity of members of the Biak Sector III Command, which is influenced by work attitude, skill level, and efficiency.

3.3 Research Location

The research location was Biak Sector III Command. The location was chosen due to the increasing public demand for satisfactory public services from this institution.

3.4 Research Variables

In this study, there are independent variables and dependent variables. These variables are: a) dependent variable: Work productivity (Y);

“Determination of Work Productivity of Members of the Biak Sector III Command: The Role of Work Attitude, Skills, and Efficiency”

and independent variables: Work attitude (X1); Skill level (X2); efficiency (X3).

3.5 Data Types and Sources

The data used are quantitative. This study utilizes both primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected by distributing questionnaires to respondents, with the questions developed by the researcher. Secondary data used to support the primary data consists of administrative records obtained from documents at the Biak Sector III Command.

3.6 Research Instruments and Research Instrument Testing

The instrument used in this study was a questionnaire, structured in the form of declarative sentences. An instrument is considered valid if it can measure what is desired and accurately capture data on the variables described. Reliability testing assesses the extent to which an instrument produces relatively similar results when repeated measurements are taken on the same subjects.

3.7 Population and Sampling Techniques

In this study, the population is all 68 Tamtama and Bintara members in the Operational Service at the Biak Sector III Command. Considering the population size is not too large, a census study was used: all 68 Tamtama and Bintara members in the Operational Service of the Biak Sector III Command will be studied as a whole. Thus, this study is a census study.

3.8 Data collection technique

Data collection is a systematic, standardized procedure for obtaining data for analysis. In this study, the author selected several techniques based on the research design, namely questionnaires, interviews, and documentation.

3.9 Data Analysis Techniques

The data analysis in this study used the following techniques: descriptive analysis, multiple linear regression, classical assimilation, and hypothesis testing.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Result

The results of the tabulation of classification according to gender of members of the Biak Sector III Command are presented in the table below:

Table 1. Respondents by Gender

No	Gender	Number of Respondents	Percentage %
1.	Man	52	76.5%
2.	Woman	16	23.5%
		68	100%

Source: Processed data, 2025

Based on the table above, 16 respondents (23.5%) were female, and 52 (76.5%) were male. Thus, the number of male respondents is greater.

The tabulation results by age for members of the Biak Sector III Command are presented in the table below:

Table 2. Respondents by Age

No	Age (Years)	Number of Respondents	Percentage %
1.	<30 years	15	22.1%
2.	31-40 years	9	13.2%
3.	41-50 years	33	48.5%
4.	>50 years	11	16.2%
		68	100%

Source: Processed data, 2025

Based on Table 4 above, the majority of respondents are in the 41-50 age group, with 33 people (48.5%). Generally, this indicates that most members of the Biak Sector III Command are in an age group with a high level of experience and knowledge.

The results of the tabulation of education for members of the Biak Sector III Command are presented in the table below:

Table 3. Respondents Based on Education

No	Age (Years)	Number of Respondents	Percentage %
1.	SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	16	23.5%
2.	Diploma	16	23.5%
3.	Bachelor	18	26.5%
4.	Postgraduate	18	26.5%
		68	100%

Source: Processed data, 2025

Based on Table 5 above, the largest group is respondents with undergraduate and postgraduate degrees, at 18 people (26.5%). Overall, this indicates that the educational level of members of the Biak Sector III Command demonstrates a good understanding of work-related issues.

The tabulation results according to the length of service of members of the Biak Sector III Command are presented in the table below:

“Determination of Work Productivity of Members of the Biak Sector III Command: The Role of Work Attitude, Skills, and Efficiency”

Table 4. Respondents Based on Work Period

No	Age (years)	Number of Respondents	Percentage %
1.	<5 years	11	16.2%
2.	6-10 years	29	42.6%
3.	11-20 years	21	30.9%
4.	>20 years	7	10.3%
		68	100%

Source: Processed data, 2025

Based on Table 6 above, the largest group is respondents with 6-10 years of service, at 29 people (42.6%). Generally, this indicates that the majority of members of the Biak Sector III Command have served for 6-10 years.

The frequency distribution of each indicator of variable (X1) is described in the following table: responsibility in work is obtained that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 35 respondents or 51.5%; seeking additional information to increase knowledge is obtained that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 35 respondents or 51.5%; feeling appreciated by colleagues is obtained that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 37 respondents or 54.4%; feeling motivated to come to work is obtained that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 32 respondents or 47.1%; completing work carefully is obtained that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 33 respondents or 48.5%; maintaining communication with colleagues is obtained that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 32 respondents or 47.1%.

The frequency distribution of each indicator of variable (X2) is described in the following table: being able to identify priorities in work is obtained that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 31 respondents or 45.6%; implementing work procedures is obtained that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 37 respondents or 54.4%; having sufficient access to information is obtained that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 35 respondents or 51.5%; there are aspects of procedures that need to be improved is obtained that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 38 respondents or 55.9%; working well without supervision is obtained that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 39 respondents or 57.4%; having skills relevant to the job is obtained that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 25 respondents or 36.8%.

The frequency distribution of each indicator of variable (X3) is described in the following table: motivated to achieve the established work goals, it was found that the majority of respondents answered in agreement, namely 39 respondents or 57.4%; clearly understanding the work goals, it was found that the majority of respondents answered in

agreement, namely 36 respondents or 52.9%; income information is clear enough, it was found that the majority of respondents answered in agreement, namely 25 respondents or 36.8%; management or superiors support efforts to save resources in the workplace, it was found that the majority of respondents answered in agreement, namely 34 respondents or 50.0%; saving the use of resources, it was found that the majority of respondents answered in agreement, namely 39 respondents or 57.4%; efforts to save resources have been implemented sufficiently, it was found that the majority of respondents answered in agreement, namely 40 respondents or 58.8%.

The frequency distribution of each indicator of variable (Y) is described in the following table: able to analyze data and information well, it was found that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 30 respondents or 44.1%; feeling that they have the ability to overcome problems, it was found that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 31 respondents or 45.6%; feeling that they have high work enthusiasm, it was found that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 29 respondents or 42.6%; feeling very productive, it was found that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 44 respondents or 64.7%; Biak Sector III Command provides facilities for self-development of members, it was found that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 30 respondents or 44.1%; feeling that they have sufficient support from the surrounding area, it was found that the majority of respondents answered agree, namely 40 respondents or 58.8%.

Table 5. Recapitulation of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Variables	Information	Regression Coefficient	t Count	Sig.
X1	Work Attitude	.014	0.150	.881
X2	Skill Level	.093	1,037	.303
X3	Efficiency	.112	1,175	.244
Constant	18,329			
R2	.032			
Adjusted R Square	.013			
F Count	5,714			
Sig. F	.000			
N	68			
Dependent variable = (Y)				

Source: Processed data, 2025

Based on the regression table, a multiple linear regression equation can be prepared as follows:

$$Y = a + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + e$$

The regression constant of 18.329 indicates that even when the independent variable is set to 0, there is still an effect on the performance of members in the Biak Sector III Command. The regression coefficient for X1 (0.014) indicates that X1 has a positive influence on the performance of members of the Biak Sector III Command. The t-test results indicate that the probability value of variable X1 is less than the researcher's error rate of 0.05. The regression coefficient for X2 (0.093) indicates that X2 has a positive influence on the performance of members of the Biak Sector III Command. The t-test results indicate that the probability value of variable X2 is less than the researcher's error rate of 0.05. The regression coefficient for variable X3 (0.112) indicates that X3 has a positive influence on the performance of members of the Biak Sector III Command. The t-test results indicate that the probability value of variable X3 is less than the researcher's error rate of 0.05.

The relationship between the independent variables (X1, X2, X3) and the dependent variable (Y) can be measured using a multiple correlation coefficient. The resulting R value (correlation coefficient) of 0.032 indicates that the correlation between the independent and dependent variables is 32%. This figure indicates a strong relationship between the researcher-selected independent variables and the dependent variable. The R2 (Adjusted) coefficient of determination is 0.013, indicating that the independent variables explain 13% of the variation in the dependent variable. In comparison, the remaining 87% is due to other independent variables not studied.

Hypothesis I testing in this study uses the F test to assess the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable in the Biak Sector III Command. Based on the F test results, the calculated F value is 5.714, with a significance level. F of 0.00 while the F table value is (3.132), for a value of 1. The comparative value between the calculated F and the F table shows that the calculated F is greater (calculated F (5.714) > F table (3.132)). And the Sig. The F value (0.000) is less than the researcher's error rate of 0.05 (5%). So the independent variables have a significant effect on the dependent variable. Thus, hypothesis I can be proven.

Hypothesis II testing in this study uses the t test, which is to test the significance of the influence of each (partial) independent variable on the dependent variable as follows: Variable X1 has a t value of 0.150 with a significance (Sig.) of 0.000; variable X2 has a t value of 1.037 with a significance (Sig.) of 0.000; variable X3 has a t value of 1.175 with a significance (Sig.) of 0.000. The results of this study indicate that the significance values (Sig. t) for the independent variables partially indicate a significant effect on member performance. Thus, hypothesis 2 can be proven.

The Unstandardized Coefficient for variable X3 (0.112) is the largest among variables X1 and X2. Thus, the third

hypothesis stating that X3 is an independent variable that has a greater or dominant influence on employee performance can be proven.

4.2 Discussion

Overview of Research Variables: Work attitude is an individual behavior that reflects a sense of responsibility, loyalty, enthusiasm, and concern for work and the organization. A positive work attitude encourages members to work harder, collaborate with the team, and maintain ethics and integrity in their work. The more positive a person's work attitude, the greater their contribution to productivity, as they complete work with enthusiasm and full awareness.

Skill levels encompass both technical and non-technical abilities individuals possess to carry out tasks effectively and efficiently. Skills can be acquired through education, training, and work experience. Highly skilled members will be faster, more precise, and more efficient in completing tasks, thus directly driving increased productivity. Work efficiency indicates the ability to produce maximum output with minimal resource use (time, energy, costs). This is related to systematic work methods, minimizing errors, and avoiding wasted time. The more efficient an individual's or a team's work methods, the higher their productivity, as time and resources are optimally utilized. Work productivity is a measure of an individual's effectiveness and efficiency in producing work output within a specific time period.

Relationships Between Research Variables: A positive work attitude fosters a productive, collaborative work environment. High skills enable members to complete tasks more quickly and accurately. Work efficiency ensures that time and resources are utilized optimally without waste. All three simultaneously contribute significantly to increasing member work productivity.

5. CONCLUSION

This study aims to analyze the influence of work attitudes, skill levels, and efficiency on the work productivity of members of the Biak Sector III Command. Based on the results of the data analysis and discussion, work attitudes, skill levels, and efficiency simultaneously have a significant influence on member work productivity. This indicates that a single factor does not determine work productivity; instead, it results from the interaction of various aspects of human resources and the work systems implemented within the organization.

Partially, work attitude, skill level, and efficiency positively influenced the work productivity of members of the Biak Sector III Command. These findings indicate that a positive work attitude encourages more responsible, performance-oriented behavior, while an adequate skill level enables members to carry out tasks more effectively and professionally. Furthermore, efficient resource utilization

plays a crucial role in achieving optimal work results with minimal resource expenditure.

Of the three independent variables studied, efficiency had the most significant influence on member work productivity. This confirms that the ability of organizations and individuals to manage time, energy, and work resources effectively is a key factor in increasing work productivity, particularly in defense organizations that demand precision, speed, and accuracy in task execution.

Overall, the results of this study reinforce human resource management theory, which holds that work attitudes, skills, and efficiency are important determinants of work productivity. These findings also provide practical implications for the leadership of the Biak Sector III Command in formulating human resource management policies that focus on fostering positive work attitudes, continuously improving skills, and strengthening an efficient work culture to support the sustainable improvement of member work productivity.

REFERENCES

1. Adha, RN, Qomariah, N., & Hafidzi, AH (2019). The Influence of Work Motivation, Work Environment, and Work Culture on the Performance of Social Service Employees in Jember Regency. *Journal of Science and Technology Research*, 4(1), 47–62.
2. Adisasmita, R. (2011). *Regional Government Management*. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
3. Anggraini, F., & Budiarti, A. (2020). The Effect of Price, Promotion, and Service Quality on Customer Loyalty Mediated by Customer Satisfaction in Gojek Consumers. *Journal of Economic Education (JUPE)*, 8(3), 86–94.
4. Endang Kustini, & Novita Sari. (2020). The Effect of Training and Work Discipline on Employee Work Productivity at PT. Bumen Redja Abadi – BSD . *Scientific Journal, Human Resource Management*, 303-311.
5. Hj. Sedarmayanti, 2019, *Human Resource Management, Bureaucratic Reform and Civil Servant Management*, Bandung, PT Refika Aditama.
6. Mantera, IGM (2007). *Human Resource Management*. Jakarta: Swasembada. Manullang, M. (2000). *Personnel Management*. 3rd Edition. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press.
7. Nimran, U. (2006). *Human Resource Management (HRM)*. Malang: UB Press. Nitisemito, AS (2007). *Personnel Management*. Revised Edition. Jakarta: PT. Ghalia Indonesia.
8. Prawirosentono, S. (2010). *Human Resource Management: Concepts, Theories, and Development in the Context of Public Organizations*. Jakarta: Graha Ilmu.
9. Raharjo, Paramita & Warso. (2016). The Influence of Work Ability, Experience, and Training on Employee Work Productivity with Work Competence as an Intervening Variable (case study at KUD "PATI KOTA" Pari Regency)—*Journal of Management*, Vol. 2, No. 2.
10. Sari GAPLP. (2020). Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). *Journal of Science & Health*, 2(4), 549-552.
11. Setiawan, O., Utari, W., & Hartati, CS (2019). The Influence of Work Motivation and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance at the Kapas Community Health Center
12. Bojonegoro Regency. *Journal of Management Partners (JMM Online)*, 3(5), 585– 598.
13. Setya, RT (2018). The Effect of Compensation on Workforce Productivity at PT Bunga Matahari Medan. *Simantek Scientific Journal*, 2(3), 113–121.
14. Sugiyono. (2021). *Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research Methods* (2nd ed.).
15. Sukardi. (2021). *Educational Research Methodology (Competencies and Practices, Revised Edition)*. Jakarta.
16. Sutrisno, E. (2017). *Human Resource Management*. Jakarta: Kencana.
17. Wati, Rahma, & Maria, Delli (2024). The Effect of Profitability, Capital Structure, Dividend Policy, and Liquidity on Company Value.
18. Wirawan, *Human Resource Performance Evaluation*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat, 2012.